

ALMEIDA, Rosane. **Cumarim, a pimenta do reino** [Cumarim, a spice girl]. Illustrations: Willian Santiago. São Paulo: FTD, 2019.

REVIEW¹

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Rosane Almeida is a 'reveller', to use the term adopted by popular artists to define their playfulness when producing art. The book hence invites the reader to play with Cumarim, a naughty and very curious little girl, by evoking popular children's games of Brazilian culture. The author co-founded the Instituto Brincante with Antônio Nóbrega, an organisation which aims to foster knowledge, assimilation, and recreation of various Brazilian forms of artistic expression, with a view to celebrating the rich national culture and the importance of its diversity.

Keywords: Folklore. Legend. folk tradition.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2020 Bologna. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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